

Maintenance of Peace and Development of Host Communities through Corporative Social Responsibility a Study of MTN in Onitsha South LGA of Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

This Paper is concerned with the maintenance of peace and development of host communities through corporative social responsibility a study of MTN in Onitsha South L.G.A of Anambra State. Specific objectives investigated includes: The existence of corporate social responsibility in Onitsha South, whether MTN has corporate social responsibility programme in Onitsha South, the level of impact MTN corporate social responsibility programme has on the development and peace building in of Onitsha South, whether MTN corporate social responsibility programme contributes to maintenance of peace in Onitsha. This lead to formation of three research questions, are there existences of corporate social responsibility in Onitsha South? Does MTN have corporate social responsibility programme for development of Onitsha South? To what extent has MTN corporate social responsibility programme impacted on the development and peace building in Onitsha South? Is there any significant relationship between MTN corporate social responsibility programme and maintenance of peace in Onitsha South? The conceptual review, theoretical review and empirical review were used to through more lights on the research. The research employed a descriptive survey design to answer the three research questions. A questionnaire was designed and administered to the sample size of 399 subjects to find answers to the research questions. From the 399 copies of questionnaire distributed to the 399 respondents, 395 copies were returned while 4 copies were not returned. Therefore, a total of 395 questionnaire representing 98,99% of the respondents were used for the finally analysis below

INTRODUCTION

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) programmes are being used in recent time to maintain peaceful relationship between the companies and the host communities where the companies are sited. Through maintenance of good and healthy Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) programme, the act of peace building is made through provisions of needed social amenities, jobs and reduction in environmental insecurity, which invariably aids development. Developed countries for instance, have well established legal documents and standard policies which specify the roles corporate bodies have to play for the welfare of society. In Ghana however, not even a single official document for CSR is available (Afrane and Adjei Poku, 2013). The need for social Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) programme is paramount in maintenance of peace in the host communities through the development programmes the companies provides for the host communities.

Development is the result of society's capacity to organize the resources to meet challenges and opportunities. Society passes through well define stages in the cause of its development (Wikipedia, 2021). Initially, around 1980's, many scholars explored and identify the effects of globalisation and global capitalism as the best system with regard to contributing to wealth creation and development. But in the mid 1990's, the failures of the system, like the huge income gaps between nations, were beginning to become obvious. This leads to the debate concerned with the need for a strong and moral ecology which reflects the wider social and cultural mores of society. For this ecology to be developed there is a need for support, not only from governments, but from all stakeholders, not the least from the private business sector (Apatira, 2010).

In the quest for greater contribution to wealth creation and development, and maintenance of peaceful relationship between corporate companies and host communities, the concept of corporate social responsibility becomes very much relevance both in theory and in practices. Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a concept rooted in modern business thinking that corporations have an obligation to consider the interest of customers, employees, shareholders, communities and environmental factors in all aspects of their operations. This obligation is seen to extend beyond their statutory obligation to comply with legislations (Wikipedia, 2021). Corporate Social Responsibility is closely linked with the Principles of Sustainable Development, which argues that enterprises should make decisions based, not only on financial factors, such as, profits and dividends, but also based on the immediate and long-term social and environmental consequences of their activities. Notably, through sustainable development with corporate social responsibility as an agent of achieving that, peace building will be achieved. Corporate social responsibility is a commitment to improve community well-being through discretionary business practices and contributions of corporate resources. In this context, a business goes out of its way voluntarily to provide help in kind or make direct financial contributions to make life better in the society (Kotler and Nancy, 2015).

There is high evidence of underdevelopment of the Nigerian society and most specifically in Onisha South Local Government in Anambra state. This

could be shown on the part of inadequate social amenities and infrastructures in the state and Onitsha South L.G.A in particular. Also, high level of poverty which result to crime rate and insecurity of the community is worthy of note. The town like other part of Nigeria also suffers high rate of illiteracy as a result of poverty and lack of adequate environment for academics. The existence of corporate social responsibility in this area is questionable. Sometimes, this frustrates the host communities which lead to aggressive actions and reactions that negate peace in the society.

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. Are there existences of corporate social responsibility in Onitsha South?
2. Does MTN have corporate social responsibility programme for development of Onitsha South?
3. To what extent has MTN corporate social responsibility programme impacted on the development and peace building in Onitsha South?
4. Is there any significant relationship between MTN corporate social responsibility programme and maintenance of peace in Onitsha South?

LITERATURE REVIEW

State of Development in Nigeria

Development as earlier mentioned in its conceptualization is best measured by the welfare of the people and not only by increase in the national income and Gross Domestic Product (GDP) rather, it transcends the living standard such as consumption level, poverty, literacy level, employment, maternal and infant mortality, life expectancy, security etc. Nigeria has an estimated population of 170 million which makes it the most populous country in Africa and accounting for 18% of the region's population. About 51,7% of the population still resides in the rural areas leaving 48,3% in the urban centers. A proven reserve of 37 billion barrels of crude oil and 187 trillion standard cubic feet of natural gas with substantial reserve of tin, columbite, granite, iron ore etc can be credited to the Nigerian state and yet endemic poverty has continued to ravage the citizens (Federal Ministry of Environment, 2017).

Corporate Social Responsibility the Driving Forces in Nigeria

To be able to understand CSR from a Nigerian perspective it is of value to explore the drivers for, and the history and development of CSR in Nigeria. The World Business Council for Sustainable Development has discussed CSR with business and non business stakeholders in a number of countries in the world with the objective of understanding local perspectives better and to get different perceptions of what CSR should mean from a number of different societies (<https://www.cecodes.org.co>). One important finding in this study was that people were talking about the role of the private sector in relation to a social agenda and they saw that role as increasingly linked to the overall well being of society. Therefore the chosen priorities differed according to the perception of local needs (Emejo, 2018).

The key CSR issues identified in the study were:

- a. Human rights
- b. Employee rights

- c. Environmental protection
- d. Community involvement
- e. Supplier relations

Even though stakeholders across the world agreed on the importance of these issues there were regional differences with regard to priorities and understanding. For example, the understanding and definition of human rights varied between the regions. Company relations with suppliers and contractors were not always viewed as priority. In Asia and Africa, although recognizing the importance, many felt that other issues are more important.

Corporate Social Responsibility Development in Nigeria

The debate over Africa's future has been on the agenda recently with the publications of "Our Common Interest" (<http://www.commissionforafrica.org>). The report calls for "improved governance and capacity building, the pursuit of peace and security, investment in people, economic growth and poverty reduction, and increased and fairer trade". Businesses obviously have an important role in this transformation process, where a lot of efforts can be embedded within the framework of CSR.

Corporate Social Responsibility, Peace and Development

Peace is generally defined as the absence of war, fear, conflict, anxiety, suffering and violence, and about peaceful coexistence. Best asserts that it is primarily concerned with creating and maintaining a just order in society and the resolution of conflict by nonviolent means. Peace is a precious state of affairs that ushers in tranquility and development in a given environment. It is also seen as respect and tolerance between people and also a balance in and with the ecosphere. It is observed that violent conflicts (absence of peace) is a major hindrance to the development of Nigeria and other African Countries. Violence inflicts human uprising.

Multinational Corporations (MNCs)

The term Multinational Corporation (MNC) can be defined and described from differing perspectives and on a number of various levels including law, sociology, history and strategy as well as from the perspectives of business ethics and society. Multinational corporations are companies which seek to operate strategically on a global scale. A multinational corporation is a company, firm or enterprise that operates worldwide with its headquarters in a metropolitan or developed country, defines Multinational Enterprise as any business that has productive activities in two or more countries. Certain characteristics of Multinational Corporations should be identified at the start since they serve, in part, as their defining features. Often referred to as "multinational enterprises" and in some early documents of the United Nations they are called "transnational organizations". Multinational Corporations are usually very large corporate entities that while having their base of operations in one nation the "home nation" carry out and conduct business in at least one other, but usually many nations, in what are called the "host nations". Multinational Corporations are usually very large entities having a global presence and reach Multinational Corporations (MNCs) can spur economic activities in developing countries and provide an opportunity to improve the qualities of life, economic growth, and regional and global commons.

MTN Nigeria

MTN Nigeria is part of the MTN Group, Africa's leading cellular telecommunications company. On May 16, 2001, MTN became the first GSM network to make a call following the globally lauded Nigerian GSM auction conducted by the Nigerian Communications Commission earlier in the year. Thereafter the company launched full commercial operations beginning with Lagos, Abuja and Port Harcourt. MTN paid \$285m for one of four GSM licenses in Nigeria in January 2001. To date, in excess of US\$1.8 billion has been invested building mobile telecommunications infrastructure in Nigeria. Since launch in August 2001, MTN has steadily deployed its services across Nigeria. It now provides services in 223 cities and towns, more than 10,000 villages and communities and a growing number of highways across the country, spanning the 36 states of the Nigeria and the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. Many of these villages and communities are being connected to the world of telecommunications for the first time ever. The study utilized the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) for the result analysis. The result found that there is a significant relationship between corporate social responsible and development and peace building in the South West Nigeria.

Hypotheses

The researcher posited the following hypotheses to guide the study:

Hypothesis 1:

H0: There is no existence of corporate social responsibility in Onitsha South

H1: There are existences of corporate social responsibility in Onitsha South

Hypothesis 2:

H0: MTN does not have corporate social responsibility programme for development of Onitsha South.

H2: MTN have corporate social responsibility programme for development of Onitsha South.

Hypothesis 3:

H0: MTN corporate social responsibility programme have not impacted on the development and peace building in Onitsha South.

H3: MTN corporate social responsibility programme have impacted on the development peace building in Onitsha South.

Hypothesis 4:

H0: There is no significant relationship between MTN corporate social responsibility programme and maintenance of peace in Onitsha.South.

H4: There is significant relationship between MTN corporate social responsibility programme and maintenance of peace in Onitsha South.

METHODOLOGY

Sampling Technique and Sample Size Determination

Convenient sampling technique was employed. The MTN in Onitsha South was chosen as a case study because it's close to the researcher, thereby it will be convenience for the researcher to study the area without wasting much time and capitals. Also, the characteristic in MTN in Onitsha South is the same

with other MTN outlets in other parts of Nigeria, therefore it was chosen to represent other MTN outlets in other parts of Nigeria, as the findings from Onitsha South can be attributed to the other outlets in Nigeria. In determining the sample size of the study, the researcher drew the population form from Onitsha South South Local Government, with a population of 189,049 (National Population Commission, 2006). The sample was distributed to involve the residents of Onitsha South, including staffs of MTN in Onitsha South. This population number was too large to cover adequately, so the researcher applied Taro Yamane's formula so as to get the sample size of the population for effective and efficient study.

The sample size for the study was calculated using Taro Yamani formula for sample size determination as shown below:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

e= 0.05 level of significance

N= Total population

n=Desired sample

Substituting n=?

N = 189,049

e = 0.05

1 = Constant

$$\begin{aligned} n &= \frac{189,049}{1 + 189,049 (0.05)^2} \\ &= \frac{189,049}{1 + 189,049 (0.0025)} \\ &= \frac{189,049}{1 + 472.6} \\ &= \frac{189,049}{473.6} \\ &= 399.17 \\ &= 399 \text{ (by approximation)} \end{aligned}$$

There, our sample size is 399

Sources of Data Collection

Both primary and secondary sources of data were used.

Method of Data Collection

Questionnaire was instrument for data collection. 399 questionnaires were distributed to the respondents. The researcher and four assistants were engaged with the distribution and collection of the questionnaire to the respondents. The questionnaire were filled by the respondents and returned on the spot. Out of the 399 copies of questionnaire distributed, 395 copies were

returned while 4 copies were not returned. The 395 questionnaire returned represented 98,9% of the total questionnaire distributed, thereby is adequate to represent the total sample size of the study.

Table .1 Administration of Questionnaire

<i>Details</i>	<i>Number of Copies</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Copies Administered	399	100 %
Copies Returned	395	98.9 %
Unreturned Copies	4	1.1 %

Source: Researchers field survey 2023

Method of Data Analysis

In analyzing the data collected for this work, the descriptive statistics, The Statistical Package for Social Science version 20,0 (SPSS) was used to compute the data. The research questions and the hypotheses were both analyzed and tested using Pearson’s product moment correlation coefficient on SPSS software.

Decision Rule: If the coefficient value is greater than the alpha level of significant, reject the null hypothesis but if the coefficient value is less than the alpha level of significant, accept the null hypothesis.

RESULTS AND DISSCUSION

Data Presentation

1. Section A: Analysis of Biographical Information

Table 2. Sex of the Respondents

Respondents	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Male	235	59.5%
Female	160	40.5%
Total	395	100%

Source: Researchers Field Survey 2023

Figure 1. Sex of the Respondents

Table 3. Age of Respondents

Respondents	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Below 20years	0	0
20 – 29 years	85	21.5%
30 – 39 years	99	25.1%
40 – 49 years	110	27.8%
50 yrs and above	101	25.6%
Total	395	100%

Source: Researchers Field Survey 2023

Figure 2. Shows that no respondents Source: Chat in Microsoft Office Word Microsoft Excel, 2023

Figure 2. Shows that no respondents is below 20 years while 21,5%, 25,1% and 25,6% are between the age of 20-29 years, 30-39 years and 50 years and above respectively. The majority which consists of 27,8% are between the age of 40-49 years. The distribution shows that the respondents are old enough to understand the role of corporate social responsibility with regards to MTN, Onitsha South.

Table 4. Educational Qualification of Respondents

Respondents	No. of Respondents	Percentage
FSLC	5	1.3%
SSCE/GCE	35	8.9%
OND/NCE	80	20.3%
B.Sc/HND	120	30.3%
Masters and above	155	39.2%
others (specify)	0	0
Total	395	100%

Source: Researchers Field Survey 2023

Figure 3. Educational Qualification of Respondents
 Source: Chat in Microsoft Office Word Microsoft Excel, 2023

Figure 3. Above shows that 1,3% of the respondents are FLSC holder; 8,9% of the respondents are SSCE/GCE holder 20,3% of the respondents are OND/NCE holder 30,3% of the respondents are BSc/HND holder while 39,2% of the respondents are Master level holders and above. This shows that the respondents are academically sound and capable of understanding the questionnaire and able to present concrete answers to the questions in the questionnaire.

Table 5. Year of Residence in Onitsha South

Respondents	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Less than 5years	81	20.5%
5 - 10years	103	26.1%
11years and above	211	53.4%
Total	395	100%

Source: Researchers Field Survey 2023

Figure 4. Year of Residence in Onitsha South
 Source: Chat in Microsoft Office Word Microsoft Excel, 2023

Figure 4. above shows the years of residence of the respondents in Onitsha South. 20,5% of the respondents have resided in Onitsha South for less than 5 years 26,1% of the respondents have resided in Onitsha South for period

of 5-10 years, while 53,4% of the respondents have resided in Onitsha South for period of 11 years and above. This shows that the respondents have resided in Onitsha South enough time to witness or ascertain the level of existence of cooperate social responsibilities in the town.

Table 6. Position in the Society

Respondents	No. of Respondents	Percentage
MTN staff	60	15.2%
Civil servant	60	15.2%
Traders	100	25.3%
Public servant	60	15.2%
Others (general public)	115	29.1%
Total	395	100%

Source: Researchers Field Survey 2023

Figure 5. Position in the Society

Source: Chat in Microsoft Office Word Microsoft Excel, 2023

The figure above shows that 15,2% of the respondents are MTN staffs, 15,2% of the respondents are civil servants, 25,3% of the respondents are traders, 15,2% of the respondents are public servants and 29,1% of the respondents are other general public not listed.

2. Section B: Are there existences of corporate social responsibility in Onitsha South?

Table 7. Mean Response to Research Question I

S/N0	Items	X	SD	Decision
1	The level of development in Onitsha South shows that there is low level of corporate social responsibility in the area.	3.75	0.09	Accept
2	The level of corporate social responsibility in Onitsha South is high	1.97	0.52	Rejected
3	Corporate social responsibility is just an illusion in Onitsha South.	3.94	0.72	Accept

4	Most institutions/organisations in Onitsha South exploit the community rather than supporting them.	3.90	0.81	Accept
5	Companies in Onitsha South generates revenues though not adequate for development of the area	3.81	0.74	Accept
6	There is high level of misappropriation and misapplication of revenues meant for development in Onitsha South	4	0.41	Accept
Grand Mean (x)		3.91		Accept

Source: Researchers Field Survey 2023

Table 7. Shows the opinion of different respondents as well as their mean score on the existence of corporate social responsibility in Onitsha South, Anambra State. From the presentation, the level of development in Onitsha South shows that there is low level of corporate social responsibility in the area. This is supported by a mean score of 3,75. The item two that stated that the level of corporate social responsibility in Onitsha South is high is rejected with a mean score of 1,97. Corporate social responsibility is just an illusion in Onitsha South. This response is supported by mean score of 3,94. Most institutions/organisations in Onitsha South exploit the community rather than supporting them. This response is backed by the mean score 3,90. Companies in Onitsha South generates revenues though not adequate for development of the area. The mean score is 3,81. There is high level of misappropriation and misapplication of revenues meant for development in Onitsha South. This was supported by a mean score of 3,12.

Research Question 2. Does MTN Have Corporate Social Responsibility Programme for Development of Onitsha South?

Table 8. Mean Response to Research Question 2

S/N0	ITEMS	X	SD	Decision
7	MTN has a social contract in Onitsha South	3.55	0.10	Accepted
8	MTN has corporate policies that benefit the environment.	3.76	0.71	Accepted
9	MTN has a work safety initiative in Onitsha South	3.62	0.62	Accept
10	MTN has demonstrated reduction of operational impacts on climate and air pollution in Onitsha South	3.60	0.17	Accept
11	MTN has contributed in enhancing health of community dwellers and sponsoring voluntary community development	3.62	0.62	Accept

	programmes in Onitsha South.			
12	MTN has education initiatives for Onitsha South residents.	4.08	0.41	Accept
13	MTN has engaged in lots of awareness initiatives such as supports to the National Action Committee Against Aids (NACA), through the sponsorship of its HIV-AIDS awareness campaign and other related awareness projects to Onitsha South Communities	3.60	0.17	Accept
14	MTN has also engaged in poverty alleviation programmes to help the poor and unemployed youths in Onitsha South.	3.62	0.62	Accept
15	Generally, MTN has a corporate social responsibility programme for development of Onitsha South	4.08	0.41	Accept
<i>Grand Mean (x)</i>			3.43	Accept

Source: Researchers Field Survey, 2023

Table 8. Shows the opinion of different respondents as well as their mean score, on whether MTN have corporate social responsibility programme for development of Onitsha South. From the analysis, MTN has a social contract in Onitsha South. This is supported by a mean score of 3,55 which shows that it is accepted by the majority of the respondents. MTN has corporate policies that benefit the environment. Support to this response is backed by a mean score of 3,76 which is accepted. MTN has a work safety initiative in Onitsha South. This response is supported by mean score of 3,62 which is accepted. MTN has demonstrated reduction of operational impacts on climate and air pollution in Onitsha South. The mean score of respondents is 3,60. MTN has contributed in enhancing health of community dwellers and sponsoring voluntary community development programmes in Onitsha South. This response is supported by a mean score of 3,62. MTN has education initiatives for Onitsha South residents. The mean score of respondents is 4,08. MTN has engaged in lots of awareness initiatives such as supports to the National Action Committee Against Aids (NACA), through the sponsorship of its HIV-AIDS awareness campaign and other related awareness projects to Onitsha South Communities. The mean score of respondents is 3,60. MTN has also engaged in poverty alleviation programmes to help the poor and unemployed youths in Onitsha South. This response is supported by a mean score of 3,62. Generally, MTN has a corporate social responsibility programme for development of Onitsha South. The mean score of respondents is 4,08.

Research Question 3. To What Extent has MTN Corporate Social Responsibility Programme Impacted on the Development of Onitsha South?

Table 9. Mean Response to Research Question 3

S/N0	Items	X	SD	Decision
16	The company has contributed in unemployment in Onitsha South	3.75	0.09	Accept
17	There is increase literacy level as a result of MTN corporate social responsibility in Onitsha South	4.97	0.41	Accept
18	There is increase structural development as a result of MTN corporate social responsibility in Onitsha South	3.94	0.72	Accept
19	There is increase health facilities and health education as a result of MTN corporate social responsibility in Onitsha South	3.90	0.81	Accept
20	MTN has contributed to development of Onitsha South to large extent	3.81	0.74	Accept
Grand Mean (x)		3.91		Accept

Source: Researchers Field Survey, 2023

Table 9. Shows the opinion of different respondents as well as their mean score on the extent has MTN corporate social responsibility programme impacted on the development of Onitsha South. From the analysis, the company has contributed in unemployment in Onitsha South. This is supported by a mean score of 3,75. There is increase literacy level as a result of MTN corporate social responsibility in Onitsha South. Support to this response is backed by a mean score of 4,97. There is increase structural development as a result of MTN corporate social responsibility in Onitsha South. This response is supported by mean score of 3,94. There is increase health facilities and health education as a result of MTN corporate social responsibility in Onitsha South. This response is backed by the mean score 3,90. MTN has contributed to development of Onitsha South to large extent. The mean score is 3,81.

Research Question 4. Is There Any Significant Relationship Between MTN Corporate Social Responsibility and Maintenance of Peace in Onitsha South?

Table 10. Mean Response to Research Question 4

S/N0	ITEMS	X	SD	Decision
21	MTN corporate social responsibility programmes has contributed to peace building	3.55	0.10	Accepted
22	MTN Support to the security system in Onitsha South has helped in maintenance of safety and peace.	3.76	0.71	Accepted
23	MTN has added to the peace education and	3.62	0.62	Accept

	awareness of the society.			
10	MTN corporate social responsibility programmes has encouraged peaceful co-existence between the host communities and the company.	3.60	0.17	Accept
<i>Grand Mean (x)</i>			3.43	Accept

Source: Researchers Field Survey, 2023

Table 10. Shows the opinion of different respondents as well as their mean score, on the relationship between MTN corporate social responsibility and maintenance of peace in Onitsha South. From the analysis, MTN corporate social responsibility programmes have contributed to peace building. This is supported by a mean score of 3,55 which shows that it is accepted by the majority of the respondents. MTN Support to the security system in Onitsha South has helped in maintenance of safety and peace. Support to this response is backed by a mean score of 3,76 which is accepted. MTN has added to the peace education and awareness of the society. This response is supported by mean score of 3,62 which is accepted. MTN corporate social responsibility programmes has encouraged peaceful coexistence between the host communities and the company. The mean score of respondents is 3,60.

Research Hypothesis One:

H0: The level of corporate social responsibility in Onitsha South is not low

H1: The level of corporate social responsibility in Onitsha South is low

Table 11. Statistical Package for Social Science Result

		Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in Onitsha South	Low level of existence
CSR in Onitsha South	Pearson correlation	1	0.83*
			.000
Sig(2-tailed)		162	162
	N		
Low level of existence	Pearson correlation	0.83*	1
		.000	
Sig(2-tailed)	N	0.62	162

Sources: SPSS version 20.0

Table 11. Shows there is a significant relationship between CSR and low level of existence in Onitsha South. The result indicated 0,83 level of correlation coefficient which shows that corporate social responsibility existence is low in Onitsha South, Nigeria, and this is significant. The result was tested at 5% alpha

level of significance and found that the correlation coefficient value 0,83 is greater than the 0,05 alpha level of significant. The hypothesis one which says that the level of corporate social responsibility in Onitsha South is not low is hereby reject. Therefore we conclude that the level of corporate social responsibility in Onitsha South is low.

Research Hypothesis Two:

H0: MTN does not have corporate social responsibility programme for development of Onitsha South.

H2: MTN have corporate social responsibility programme for development of Onitsha South.

Table 10. Answers research question 2 as well as hypothesis 2 tested at 0.05 level of significant.

Table 12. Statistical Package for Social Science Result

		MTN	CSR for dev. of Onitsha South
MTN	Pearson Correlation	1	0.78*
			.000
information			162
Sig(2-tailed)		162	
	N		
CSR for dev. of Onitsha South	Pearson Correlation	0.78*	1
		.000	
Sig(2-tailed)	N	162	162

Sources: SPSS version 20.0

Table 12. Shows that MTN has CSR for development of Onitsha South to high extent. The result indicated 0,78 level of correlation coefficient which shows that award MTN has a corporate social responsibility (CSR) for development of Onitsha South. The result was tested at 5% alpha level of significance and found that the correlation coefficient value 0,78 is greater than the 0,05 alpha level of significant. The hypothesis two which says that MTN does not have corporate social responsibility programme for development of Onitsha South is hereby rejected. Therefore, we concluded that MTN have corporate social responsibility programme for development of Onitsha South.

Research Hypothesis Three:

H0: MTN corporate social responsibility programme have not impacted on the development and peace building in Onitsha South.

H3: MTN corporate social responsibility programme have impacted on the development peace building in Onitsha.

Table 13. Statistical Package for Social Science Result

		MTN's CSR	Development of Onitsha South
MTN's CSR	Pearson correlation	1	0.83*
			.000
Sig(2tailed)	N	162	162
Dev. of Onitsha South	Pearson correlation	0.83*	1
		.000	
Sig(2tailed)	N	162	162

Sources: SPSS version 20.0

The result above shows that the calculated SPSS 4,7 shows that MTN corporate social responsibility programmes have impacted the development of Onitsha South. The result indicated 0,83 level of correlation coefficient which shows that MTN's CSR programme make a positive impact on development of Onitsha South, and this is significant. The result was tested at 5% alpha level of significance and found that the correlation coefficient value 0,83 is greater than the 0,05 alpha level of significant. The hypothesis three (null hypothesis) which says that MTN corporate social responsibility programme have not impacted on the development of Onitsha South is hereby rejected. Therefore we conclude that MTN corporate social responsibility programme have impacted on the development of Onitsha South.

Research Hypothesis Four:

H0: MTN does not have corporate social responsibility programme for development of Onitsha South.

H4: MTN have corporate social responsibility programme for development of Onitsha South.

Table 12. Answers research question 4 as well as hypothesis 4 tested at 0,05 level of significant.

Table 14. Statistical Package for Social Science Result

		MTN	Peace in Onitsha South
MTN	Pearson Correlation	1	0.78*
			.000
information			162
Sig(2-tailed)	N	162	
Peace in. Onitsha South	Pearson Correlation	0.78*	1
		.000	
Sig(2-tailed)	N	162	162

Sources: SPSS version 20,0

Table 14. Shows that MTN has a positive relationship with maintenance of peace in Onitsha South. The result indicated 0,78 level of correlation

coefficient which shows that award MTN has a corporate social responsibility (CSR) which has contributed positively towards maintenance of peace in Onitsha South. The result was tested at 5% alpha level of significance and found that the correlation coefficient value 0,78 is greater than the 0.05 alpha level of significant. The hypothesis four which says that there is no significant relationship between MTN corporate social responsibility programme and maintenance of peace in Onitsha South is hereby rejected. Therefore, we concluded that there is significant relationship between MTN corporate social responsibility programme and maintenance of peace in Onitsha South.

Finding of the Study

The following findings are made from the research work based on the hypotheses posited:

1. The level of corporate social responsibility in Onitsha South is low
2. MTN have corporate social responsibility programme for development of Onitsha South
3. MTN corporate social responsibility programme have impacted on the development of Onitsha South
4. There is significant relationship between MTN corporate social responsibility programme and maintenance of peace in Onitsha South

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

From the findings, this study concludes that MTN has a corporate social responsibility programmes in Onitsha South which they have tried to some extent to accomplish, nevertheless, the high level of poverty and underdevelopment as seen in the Onitsha South today, even with existence of companies, showed that corporate social responsibility has not been sufficient enough to improve sufficient development and peace building in Onitsha South.

Based on the findings and our conclusion, the following recommendations are made:

1. MTN and other multinational companies should increase their dedication to giving back to the society, by formulating a framework for CSR spending to boost the standard of live of Nigerians to the point that their social reputation will engender positive and substantial increase in their financial performance, as this is essential for their going concern in the country.
2. MTN management staffs should aligned with the management staffs of Anambra Development Board in monitoring the usage of the resource mapped out for enforcing their CSR programmes to avoid misapplication and misappropriation of the funds.
3. MTN should engage the youth of Onitsha South through empowerment programmes and employment. This will help in reducing the poverty and crime level in Onitsha South.

FURTHER RESEARCH

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on this topic "Maintenance of Peace and Development of Host Communities through Corporate Social Responsibility a Study of MTN in Onitsha South LGA of Anambra State".

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